

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO THE OIL AND GAS SECTOR FOR A GREENER WORLD

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Abstract

The application of scientific, technical and intellectual potential of innovation activity for the sake of a green world to the oil and gas sector leads to an increase in optimal and sustainable efficiency in this area. The development of innovation activity in the oil and gas sector is characterized by the state of the scientific and technical potential of this area, its qualitative and quantitative parameters. In the era of digitalization, technological innovations, being dynamic and procedural, have the opportunity to demonstrate their importance in the national oil and gas sector. In recent years, the economic effect of the Azerbaijani oil and gas sector has had a significant force in the development of science, technical and technological innovations. By properly using the innovation potential, it is possible to develop the country's oil and gas sector and thereby other sectors of the economy. For this, it is necessary, first of all, to expand innovation activity in the national oil and gas sector, and at the same time, to ensure that projects are prepared and implemented on the basis of "portfolio problems". The results of the study contribute to the expansion of methodologically justified models of the innovation process for the sake of a green world in the oil and gas sector of Azerbaijan and to improve the management of innovation processes in this sector.

Keywords: Innovation, Oil and Gas Sector, Project, Green World.

Introduction. Implementation of innovation activities and evolution of innovative models in the oil and gas industry of Azerbaijan are very important factors for ensuring competitiveness and sustainability in the rapidly changing global market. The article presents new approaches in the field of improving the innovation process applied to enterprises related to the oil and gas industry of Azerbaijan. It should be especially emphasized that local and foreign donor organizations of relevant profiles operating in Azerbaijan are interested in expanding innovations in the oil and gas sector of the republic and developing new projects in this area.

Purpose. The purpose of the article is to present new approaches to the implementation of innovative projects in the oil and gas sector of Azerbaijan for the sake of a green world and to ensure the sustainability of innovative activities in this field. At the same time, one of the main goals is to use innovation opportunities to create an ecologically clean environment, increase international recognition of the oil and gas field and attract investors.

Mission. The mission of the study is to introduce technical and technological, innovative projects in the oil and gas sector, and at the same time increase the specific weight of ecologically clean projects in enterprises for the sake of a green world.

Methodology. The results of scientific research are obtained using general and special methods of cognition: abstract logical analysis, theoretical generalization method, deduction and induction, statistical analysis.

Limitations. The main limitations of the study are financial support, difficulties in the application and use of innovative technologies, and adaptation barriers.

Literature review. The article was researched and prepared using both domestic and foreign scientific works and statistical data.

Innovations in the Oil and Gas Sector of Azerbaijan. The oil and gas industry of Azerbaijan has been considered one of the main areas of the country's economic development since the beginning of the 20th century. With the arrival of major investors such as the Rothschild and Nobel brothers in the oil and gas sector, the influx of capital in the early 20th century led to a significant increase in oil production and rapid growth in the service sector. In 1992, the State Oil Company of the Republic of Azerbaijan (SOCAR) was established on the basis of the "Azerneft State Concern" and the "Azerneftkimya" Production Association. The oil and gas sector has played an important role in the economy and cultural development of Azerbaijan (Huseynov A.G., et al. 2016).

Currently, SOCAR, the country's leading company, conducts a deeper and more accurate analysis of deposits using the most advanced technologies during exploration and minimizes the impact on the environment by adhering to the principles of environmental responsibility during production (Alguliyev R. et al. 2018). It is known that the environmental responsibility of companies operating in the oil and gas sector is important, and SOCAR has a leading position in this area. The company adheres to modern environmental standards for environmental protection during exploration and production and applies innovative solutions aimed at reducing carbon emissions. This approach demonstrates SOCAR's commitment to the principles of sustainability. SOCAR makes significant contributions to the country's economic development by using innovative technologies in the exploration and production of Azerbaijan's energy resources. The company ensures the export of our country's rich oil and gas reserves to world markets and further strengthens our country's position in the international energy market. On the other

hand, SOCAR, which pays special attention to environmental responsibility and sustainability, strives to create a cleaner and more sustainable energy environment for future generations.

SOCAR For a Green World updated and agreed on a number of environmental regulatory documents in the 2023 reporting year. These documents are as follows:

- Environmental Impact Assessment – 8 pieces;
- Discharge Limit – 9 pieces;

- Hazardous Waste Passport – 9 pieces;
 - Ecological Passport – 45 pieces;
 - Inventory document of harmful substances emitted into the atmosphere and sources of physical impact on it – 8 pieces;
 - Discharge Limit Document – 10 pieces;
 - Special permit document for water use – 2 pieces
- In addition, in 2023, scientific research and design-search-construction works were carried out at the Oil and Gas Scientific Research and Design Institute:

Diagram 1: Research activities at the institute in 2023
 Source: <https://socar.az/az/page/illik-hesabatlar>

In recent years, SOCAR has implemented a number of innovative projects related to technical innovations and technological achievements. These innovations have increased efficiency in the oil and gas sector,

environmental protection, and accelerated the transition to alternative energy sources. SOCAR's main innovative projects are implemented in the following areas (SOCAR 2024):

Figure 1: SOCAR's main innovative projects
 Source: <https://socar.az/az/home>

SOCAR has taken a number of steps to implement wind and solar energy projects in the country since 2020. These steps are aimed at reducing carbon emissions. On the other hand, the company uses artificial intelligence technologies in most operations. Regarding environmental protection, the company is implementing a number of environmental projects related to reducing waste in the oil and gas production process and reducing the level of harmful gases emitted into the atmosphere. Regarding human capital development, SOCAR improves the knowledge and skills of its em-

ployees through modern training and development programs. The company implements an internship program with 5 higher education institutions and cooperates with universities for personnel training.

In recent years, great attention has been paid to new technologies and innovative approaches in the oil and gas sector of Azerbaijan, as in every country, for the sake of a green world. A number of innovative projects are being implemented in order to increase the competitiveness of the oil and gas sector, increase production efficiency, and minimize environmental impact (Vazir Zada X., et al. 2017).

Figure 2: Innovative approaches to Azerbaijan's oil and gas sector

As in most countries of the world, the oil and gas sector in Azerbaijan contributes to the creation of a green world both nationally and globally by implementing innovative projects aimed at environmental

protection and ensuring sustainable energy development (Valiyev D.A. 2008). At the same time, these new approaches strengthen the country's ecological sustainability and support the fight against climate change

(Azerbaijan - 2020: A Look into the Future Development Concept, 2012). There are a number of principles of state regulation of innovative activity in the oil and gas sector, and these principles include: activation of investment activity; efficient use of scientific and technical potential; credit policy and tax incentives; application of complex, basic and improving innovations, etc. (Huseynov A.G. 2022).

In order to accelerate its transformation, SOCAR has launched a two-year "Climate and Sustainability – LightHouse" program. This program will support decarbonization, successfully implement the company's low-carbon initiatives, and improve the environmental performance of existing assets.

Figure 3: Initial efforts of the "LightHouse" project for 2024

Source: <https://socar.az/az/page/davamli-inkisaf-hesabatlari>

SOCAR aims to prevent the growth of emissions through its decarbonization program in order to achieve the "Net Zero" target by 2050. Through these targets,

SOCAR aims to transition from an oil and gas company to a sustainable energy company.

Figure 4: SOCAR's goals

Source: <https://socar.az/az/page/davamli-inkisaf-hesabatlari>

In recent years, the introduction of new innovative approaches to the oil and gas sector of Azerbaijan for the sake of a green world, initiated by the country's President Ilham Aliyev, leads to environmental protection and sustainable development of energy. In particular, reducing carbon emissions, investments in blue hydrogen and renewable energy sources serve to increase environmental sustainability in the sector.

At the same time, a Memorandum of Understanding was signed between the Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan, SOCAR, "PAŞA Holding" LLC and SABAH.HUB ("SABAH ACADEMY" LLC) to form, strengthen and ensure mutual coordination of the innovation ecosystem in Azerbaijan.

Conclusion. As a result of our research, we can say that the sustainable development of the country's economy requires the government to support the implementation of the following measures and approaches in the oil and gas sector for the sake of a green world.

1. Participation in financing innovative projects based on high technologies in the oil and gas sector;

2. State support for antitrust policy and competition;

3. Integration into the world economy through innovative innovations in the oil and gas sector;

4. Development of applied science by the state, increasing the demand for knowledge by both private and public organizations, as knowledge becomes the main economic resource, etc.

These innovative approaches play an important role in Azerbaijan's fight against global climate change and in fulfilling international environmental obligations in the international community. Companies operating in the oil and gas sector make significant contributions to environmental protection, while continuing the country's economic development by making traditional energy production clean and environmentally safe. As a result of innovative initiatives, the oil and gas sector of Azerbaijan is moving towards a stable and competitive future.

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